

DIRECTING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION TO PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: The task of inclusive education is to provide quality education to all children, regardless of their abilities and status. At the same time, the principle of inclusiveness implies that in order to have positive mental and social development, children with disabilities should live in a family and study together with their peers in a regular school. The article focuses on inclusive education in preschool education processes. recommendations are offered.

Key words: preschool education, inclusive education, children with disabilities, general education, educational system, educational process.

During the past period, on the establishment of an effective system of preschool education aimed at bringing the growing generation in our country to a healthy and comprehensively mature adult, introducing effective forms and methods of education and upbringing into the educational process. extensive work has been done. At the same time, the analysis carried out, ensuring children's coverage of preschool education, filling preschool educational institutions with modern educational and methodological materials and fiction, solving the issues of attracting qualified pedagogues and management personnel to the field shows the need.

In 2020-2025, a "road map" was developed for the implementation of the concept of development of inclusive education in the public education system in 2020-2021. The target indicators for the development of the education of children with special educational needs until 2025 have been approved. It was determined

that the concept will be implemented step by step on the basis of a separate "Roadmap", which will be approved annually starting from 2022, based on the achieved results, target indicators and the main directions for the relevant period. The concept will be implemented in two stages, including:

During 2020-2022: improvement of the normative base in the field of inclusive education system; training, retraining and retraining of qualified pedagogues for the inclusive education system; strengthening the material and technical base of institutions where inclusive education is introduced, providing them with special devices (lifting devices, ramps, handrails, etc.), necessary literature, methodical manuals, equipment and supplies for training in various professions ; introduction of modern information and communication technologies and innovative projects in the field of inclusive education; creating a positive social environment among the population by explaining the right to education of children with special educational needs, the essence of inclusive education; implementation of measures aimed at preventing discrimination of children with special educational needs, negative treatment of them; introduction of the inclusive education system into the activities of individual educational institutions as an experiment; During 2023-2025:

gradually introducing the inclusive education system in other general secondary education institutions; implementation of measures aimed at ensuring the right to inclusive education of every child with special educational needs; teaching methods in inclusive education are improved and the principles of individualization are gradually introduced into the educational process; in the process of inclusive education, taking measures aimed at the spiritual and moral upbringing of students, their physical healthy and energetic formation; optimization of the number of specialized state educational institutions for children with special educational needs was determined based on the physical and mental needs of students and the geographical location of educational institutions.

The mission of inclusive education is to provide quality education to all children, regardless of their abilities and status.

At the same time, the principle of inclusion implies that children with limited opportunities should live in a family and receive education in a normal school together with their peers in order to have a positive mental and social development. The inclusive education system means that a child in a wheelchair can study in any nearby school, if he/she has learning difficulties, he/she has special help to learn to read and write, and a child who does not attend classes ensures that appropriate support is provided to return to school.

The importance of inclusive education in the pre-school education system is the development of mental and physical feelings and actions of the child, while ensuring that children with disabilities receive quality education from an early age. What does inclusive education provide to children with disabilities?

- allows you to discover your own opportunities for yourself
- independent movement occurs through the opportunity to work together;
- worldview expands, life experience increases;
- the need and interest in studying increases;
- He begins to feel the same as everyone else;
- Opportunities that were not noticed before will be opened;
- Features such as bed rest and isolation disappear.

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